

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE SEMANTIC- FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE CATEGORY OF ASPECT IN AZERBAIJANI AND ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to a comparative study of the expressive features of the category of aspect in Azerbaijani and English. The main focus of the study is on how the concept of aspect is formed in both languages, by what means it is expressed, and the semantic load of this process. The article shows that the category of aspect is closely related not only to the grammatical framework, but also to the content and communicative purpose of speech. As a result of the study, it is determined that in Azerbaijani, the meaning of aspect is expressed more through suffixes and auxiliary means, and in this case, both synthetic and analytical methods operate in parallel. In English, modality is mainly realized through modal verbs and various constructions, and this system is formed more depending on the context. At the same time, the article also touches on the interaction of tense and aspect categories and explains the possibilities of some tense forms, especially the present perfect tense, to create shades of style. In addition, the finite and infinite division of verbs based on their semantic features is considered, and the role of this division in the formation of the meaning of aspect is explained on the basis of specific examples. The comparison shows that although both languages have different structures, certain semantic parallels are observed. As a result, the conclusions reached in the article once again confirm the importance of the comparative approach in the study of the category of aspect and determine the main directions for future research in this area.*

Key words: *the category of aspect, Azerbaijani language, English language, comparative linguistics, semantic features, grammatical categories, analytical and synthetic methods, time and style relationship.*

The category of aspect of the verb occupies an important place in the grammatical system of the world's languages and expresses the subject's attitude to the action in speech. The category of aspect is actively manifested not only at the logical and grammatical, but also at the semantic and communicative levels. In different languages, the expression of this category is realized through a number of lexical, morphological and syntactic means, which makes its study a particularly relevant issue. Although the Azerbaijani and English languages belong to different language families in terms of structure and origin, the existence of the concept of aspect in both languages and the expression of this concept in different ways acts as a common linguistic issue. In Azerbaijani, the category of aspect is expressed mainly by analytical and synthetic methods - through auxiliary verbs denoting modality, suffixes, lexical units and intonation. In English, aspect is realized with the help of various modal verbs and constructions, contextual means and intonation. However, there are significant differences between the structure and functional capabilities of the means of expression of aspect in these two languages. English is characterized as one of the main parts of speech, characterized by a rich and developed system of grammatical categories such as person, quantity, tense, form and style. A comparative analysis of English and

Azerbaijani shows that in both languages, the category of aspect of the verb is expressed by various formal and semantic means. However, the issue of the existence of verbs with a mode meaning still remains controversial in linguistics and gives rise to different approaches. In Azerbaijani, the mode meaning of the verb can be expressed by both synthetic (morphological) and analytical (lexical-grammatical) methods. In English, the expression system of this category is more complex and multidirectional. As in different languages, the category of aspect is implemented in English through a number of grammatical and contextual means. The aspectual forms of the verb used in the Azerbaijani language are combined into two groups according to the formation and method of expression: 1. Expression of verb aspects by synthetic method.

The synthetic method conveys the meaning in the expression of the aspect of verb directly through the verb itself, that is, through suffixes or modifications added to it. In this method, the root and suffixes of the verb combine to reflect the style category, and in this way the meaning of aspect is formed in a synthetic form. Synthetic expression is more closely related to the structure of the language, and various forms of the verb can carry the category of aspect.

2. Expression of aspect of verbs by analytical method.

In the analytical method, aspect of verbs are expressed in addition to the verb itself, through auxiliary verbs, separate words or phraseological units. In this method, the meaning of style is created as a result of the working together of several elements, and such forms can reflect the tense, case and aspect categories of the verb together. This analytical method is widely used in the expression of verb moods in the Azerbaijani language.

In English, the categories of tense and aspect operate on the basis of mutual dependence and unity. Like the category of aspect, the category of tense also reflects various mood shades according to the semantic character of the verb - that is, whether it expresses a finite (terminative) or infinite (non-terminative) action. In this regard, tense forms have the function of determining not only the time when the action occurs, but also its character and results.

In particular, the present perfect tense clearly demonstrates this relationship. When this tense form is used with verbs expressing a terminal, that is, finite action, it emphasizes the connection with the present time - more precisely, its result - of the action that occurred in the past and has already been completed. For example, in the sentence , the finite character of the verb "to break" expresses the completion of the action and its effect on the present situation. Here, the cause and effect relationship is clearly manifested. According to O.Musayev, there are no independent formal indicators expressing the meaning of style in English. Thus, the same morphological means that participate in the formation of the category of tense can also serve to express the meaning of aspect in certain cases [1, p. 137]. In addition, it should be noted that, in addition to the traditional grammatical categories of the verb, there are two more grammatical-semantic features of it that are not expressed by special formal indicators. These features are mainly related to the semantic and syntactic behavior of the verb. There are no special morphological markers, suffixes or auxiliary means to distinguish active and passive verbs in English. For this reason, they are not identified as a separate formal grammatical category. The active or passive nature of a verb can be determined only at the syntactic level, that is, based on the relationship of the verb to the object within the sentence. In addition, when analyzing verbs in English for meaning, it is

observed that the meaning of aspect is reflected to a certain extent in their lexical meanings. According to O. Musayev's approach, verbs are divided into two main groups according to their semantic properties [1, pp. 136-137]:

1. Terminative verbs

2. Non terminative verbs

- Terminative verbs have a specific and precise meaning, their use is explained in a single and clear way in a certain context;

- The meaning of terminative verbs is usually related to a specific object or subject;

For example, the action implied in the verb "to give" expresses a certain process of giving, that is, one person gives something to another person.

- Non terminative verbs have broader and more general meanings;

their meaning can change depending on the context and have more potential for meaning:

For example, the meaning of the verb "to be" can be interpreted differently in different situations, and therefore this verb has a wider semantic range. The classification we have presented above helps to understand how the meanings of verbs are formed and the expressive capabilities of the language. Also, comparing terminative verbs and non terminative verbs allows for a better understanding of the structural differences between languages. This approach also helps to make the right choices during translation work, because a verb in one language may not have exactly the same meaning as a verb in another language. The semantic range of such verbs varies depending on the context of their use, and as a result, their functions are multifaceted, both semantically and grammatically. Taking these features into account, it would be useful to analyze the following examples:

"She smiled warmly after hearing the news" → in this sentence, the semantics of the verb indicates that the action ended at a certain point, that is, its finiteness is emphasized. Here the action is completed and the result is achieved.

"He would run every morning for hours" → in this expression the meaning of the verb is indefinite; that is, the action is continuous and repetitive. Here the emphasis is not on the end of the action, but on its duration. A specific feature of English aspect forms is that the character of the action expressed in the aspect sense is always connected with a time interval. In other words, the process described by verbs in aspect forms is revealed in unity with how it occurs at a specific moment of time or in a time interval.

Accordingly, it would be more correct to name aspect forms "aspect-tense forms", because in these forms there is an unbreakable, mutual connection between aspect and tense.

When comparing the existence of aspect of verb in Azerbaijani and English, our main attention can be paid to the expression of the verb with tense forms. Since both languages belong to different language groups and are not related languages, their comparison is not easy. From this point of view, it is possible to analyze the methods of formation and expression of verb forms in both languages separately and only compare them on the basis of the obtained linguistic materials. Three main types of analytical methods are widely used in the formation of verb forms:

- Through the combination of the inflected verb with a particle and a functional-auxiliary verb;

- Through periphrastic (i.e., phrasal) forms of the verb;

- Through the use of two inflected verbs together [2, p.29].

In the Azerbaijani language, the category of aspect is formed more morphologically, that is, with suffixes and affixes. This is a characteristic feature of agglutinative languages. In agglutinative languages, grammatical meaning, including form, is revealed through suffixes sequentially added to the roots of verbs. This method of morphological formation reveals a close, organic connection between form and verb in the structure of the language.

In addition, in English, the category of aspect is expressed more analytically, with auxiliary verbs, with periphrastic forms, or with the lexical-semantic properties of verbs. This reveals an important structural difference between inflectional and analytic languages. In analytical formation, continuous and perfect aspects are formed with the use of verbs with auxiliary verbs (for example, is, are, has, have). In periphrastic constructions, aspect connected with the future are formed with to be going to, to be about to. Also, when used with modal verbs (can, may, must, should), an effective interaction between aspect and modal meaning is observed. However, in both languages, an effective interaction is observed between aspect and tense, as well as between style and modal meaning. For example, in Azerbaijani, there is a close connection between aspectual forms connected with effect, return, reciprocity, continuity, and instant and time. This ensures that the tense forms of verbs are used more precisely, more fully, and more expressively.

Similarly, in English, strong connections are created between perfect and continuous tenses. The auxiliary verbs “has” or “have” used in the perfect form create the final, final mood, and the continuous aspect with “is” used in the continuous form. The use of these forms links the semantic fields of tense and aspect, providing richer, more precise expression possibilities. As a result, verbs acquire various semantic and functional moods through morphological suffixes, which enriches the expressive possibilities of the language. The grammatical systems of both languages reveal a complex, multifaceted relationship between aspect and tense, as well as between mood and modal meaning. This relationship plays an important role in the formation, use, and creation of meaning fields of verbs, and forms functional connections between mood and tense in the grammatical structure of languages. Thus, the importance of the category of aspect as an area to be investigated is confirmed by its role in the morphological, syntactic, and semantic structure of the language.

The category of manner, which is a lexical-grammatical category of the verb with the features of a grammatical category, expresses the methods associated with the process of action of the verb (each moment of its implementation, intensity of manifestations, etc.).

The conducted research shows that the category of aspect of the verb carries an important semantic and functional load in both Azerbaijani and English languages, but the means of expression and structural features of this category are conditioned by the typological differences of the languages. While in Azerbaijani language manner is expressed mainly through the interaction of synthetic and analytical means, in English this category is realized more through modal verbs, grammatical constructions and contextual factors. During the research, it was determined that in English language there is a close connection between the categories of tense and aspect, and some tense forms, especially the present perfect tense, play an important role in the expression of shades of aspect. This shows that aspect operates not only as a separate grammatical category, but also in interaction with other categories. At the same time, the classification of verbs

into terminative and non-terminative allows us to understand their semantic features and the formation of the meaning of the mode more deeply. This division reveals such important aspects as the degree of completion of the action, its continuity, and its connection with the result. In general, the comparative analysis shows that although the Azerbaijani and English languages have different morphological systems, there are certain semantic similarities in the expression of the category of aspect. This fact once again confirms the existence of linguistic universals and reveals the importance of the comparative study of languages with different systems from a theoretical and practical point of view.

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